

IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE STATE, SOCIETY AND BUSINESS RESEARCH ON EFFECTIVE USE OF GR-MANAGEMENT MECHANISMS

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Abstract: The article examines the need and factors, goals, objectives and problems of using the GR-management mechanism in the development of the state, society and business at the present stage of liberalization and modernization of the economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The advantages and features of the effective use of the GR-management mechanism for the development of the state, society and business in the prospects for the country's socio-economic development have been scientifically substantiated. The possibilities of effective use of the GR-management mechanism in the corporate governance system of the Republic of Uzbekistan have been studied and recommendations have been developed.

Keywords: commercial and non-profit organizations, business structures, public authorities, the rights and obligations of an enterprise, freedom and public-private partnership, management of the organization's interaction with the state, GR-management mechanism.

ДАВЛАТ, ЖАМИЯТ ВА БИЗНЕС РИВОЖИДА GR -БОШҚАРУВ МЕХАНИЗМЛАРИДАН САМАРАЛИ ФОЙДАЛАНИШ БЎЙИЧА ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР

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Аннотация: Мақолада Ўзбекистон Республикасида иқтисодиёт эркинлашуви ва модернизациясининг ҳозирги босқичида давлат, жамият ва бизнес тараққиётида GR-менежмент механизмидан фойдаланиш зарурлиги ва омиллари, мақсади, вазифалари, ва муаммолари тадқиқ этилган. Мамлакат ижтимоий-иқтисодий ривожланиш истиқболларида давлат, жамият ва бизнес тараққиёти учун GR-менежмент механизмидан самарали фойдаланишнинг устунликлари ҳамда ўзига хос хусусиятлари илмий асослаб берилган. Ўзбекистон Республикаси корпоратив менежмент тизимида GR-менежмент механизмидан самарали фойдаланиш имкониятлари тадқиқ этилган ҳамда тавсиялар ишлаб чиқилган.

Калит сўзлар: тижорат ва нотижорат ташкилотлари, бизнес тузилмалари, давлат ҳокимияти органлари, корхонанинг ҳуқуқ ва мажбуриятлари, эркинлиги ва давлат-хусусий шериклиги, ташкилотнинг давлат билан ўзаро ҳаракат жараёнларини бошқариш, GR-менежмент механизми.

В РАЗВИТИИ ГОСУДАРСТВА, ОБЩЕСТВА И БИЗНЕСА ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ЭФФЕКТИВНОГО ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ МЕХАНИЗМОВ GR-МЕНЕДЖМЕНТА

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Аннотация: В статье исследуются необходимость и факторы, цели, задачи и проблемы использования механизма GR-менеджмента в развитии государства, общества и бизнеса на

современном этапе либерализации и модернизации экономики в Республике Узбекистан. Научно обоснованы преимущества и особенности эффективного использования механизма GR-менеджмента для развития государства, общества и бизнеса в перспективах социально-экономического развития страны. Изучены возможности эффективного использования механизма GR-менеджмента в системе корпоративного управления Республики Узбекистан и разработаны рекомендации.

Ключевые слова: коммерческие и некоммерческие организации, бизнес-структуры, органы государственной власти, права и обязанности предприятия, свобода и государственно- частное партнерство, управление взаимодействием организации с государством, механизм GR-менеджмента.

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Introduction

Dynamic changes in economic reality, the growing importance of globalization and information processes have led to the transformation of the relationship between business and the social sector with the state [1]. In this context, not only the boundaries between society, business and the state, but also the conditions of their interaction, the criteria and conditions of interest and responsibility are changing. The aggravation and complexity of social and economic relations are leading to the search for and creation of new mechanisms and technologies to manage the interaction of business structures and non-profit organizations with government agencies, an issue that is currently insufficiently studied by the scientific community.

The state is the most important of all the stakeholders of the institution, that is, the person who is more interested in its activities and is interested in its results. Within the legal space, any institution carries out bilateral interaction with the authorities determined by the state and is tested for its managerial impact. In addition, governments are often economic counterparties of institutions, while commercial companies supply their goods and services to government agencies. Thus, the success of the organization's activities depends on the effectiveness of managing the processes of interaction with the state.

The need to study the problems of managing the interaction of commercial and

non-profit organizations with the state is associated with the emergence of a new reality in management theory and practice - GR-management (English Government relations management).

In the context of increasing levels of state regulation of the economy, the importance of the theoretical revision of the process of managing the interaction of the enterprise with the state is growing. In addition, the relevance of the study of GR-management in the current situation is due to the fact that the active development of GR-departments within large foreign and national corporations and non-profit organizations requires the development, analysis and systematization of effective mechanisms for managing the interaction of enterprises with government.

Reforms in Uzbekistan in recent years in the formation and effective operation of the system of management of interaction with the state, in particular, the use of effective methods, models and technologies of GR-management mechanism, interaction with the state in terms of rights and obligations, freedom and public-private partnership effective organization and management, ensuring openness and transparency of this process has become one of the important issues at the level of public policy.

In conclusion, the theoretical, methodological and practical aspects of the GR-management mechanism as a tool for managing the interaction of the enterprise with the state in the Republic of Uzbekistan

are special, independent insufficient study as an object of research determines the relevance and scientific-practical significance of the topic of this scientific article.

Analysis of the relevant literature

Currently, the authors have different views on the use of GR-management mechanism in the development of the state, society and business, as well as the forms and features of their manifestation.

GR -manage performs functions in the system of relations between the state, society and business. The interaction of government, business and the public sector is a multifaceted phenomenon that has become the subject of study in a number of disciplines. The relationship between government and business is a complex, multifaceted and integrated area of social relations, the nature of which is determined by many factors: type of political system, regime, type of government, public administration. Features of the economic system, as well as historical development »» [3].

In the scientific literature, cooperation between business and government is defined as "a system of cooperation between state and local authorities, trade unions, employers' organizations and business structures in the regulation of socio-economic problems" [4].

Public-business cooperation allows to combine the advantages of the public and private sectors through economic incentives and motivation mechanisms by integrating the organizational, managerial and financial-economic potential of the business sector into the process of solving national and state problems on the basis of different systems.

It should be noted that the practice of interaction between government and business is defined as "an institutional alternative to direct forms of strengthening the role of the state in the economy (in terms of share in GDP, investment, tax burden, etc.)" [5].

As noted in the scientific literature [6], the processes of interaction between the state,

business and society in Russia in recent decades have undergone dynamic changes. The growing need for government agencies to create an effective system of cooperation with business is explained by the importance and place of the business community in the modern world, its role in social development.

The joint activity of the state, business and society can be successful only if it is based on the principles of mutual responsibility to achieve socially significant results [7]. It should be noted that trust between partners, reduction of uncertainty, intensification of joint activities ensure the effectiveness of cooperation between the state and society "[8].

However, despite the diversity of scientific approaches and theoretical research, there is no comprehensive research on the formation and effective operation of the GR-management mechanism as a tool for managing the interaction of the enterprise with the state.

It should be noted that the problems of effective management of the enterprise's interaction with the state in the digital economy in our country not fully resolved, especially since the GR-management mechanism in this process has not been studied comprehensively. In this regard, it is necessary and important to improve the study of this problem and, in general, to develop proposals and recommendations for the formation and effective operation of the GR-management mechanism as a tool for managing the interaction of the enterprise with the state.

The solution of these topical issues will serve as a basis for choosing the topic of this scientific article, defining its goals and objectives.

Research methodology. The use of methods of scientific observation, abstract-logical thinking, induction, deduction, statistical, economic, financial analysis, expert evaluation in the research process correctly, based on the fact that the path set for the research is reliable and clear.

Analysis and results:

The interaction of state, business and society is carried out through the following means:

- public-private partnership;
- state contract;
- special economic zones;
- product sharing agreements;
- concession agreements;
- technoparks;
- outsourcing;
- fundraising;
- foresight and others [9].

Fundraising is a set of ways to raise external financial and material resources needed to achieve an organization's goals. Non-governmental non-profit organizations use fundraising methods to cooperate with the authorities in the implementation of socially significant activities.

Foresight is a technology for studying the directions of development of a society and shaping the priorities of technological, economic and social growth. Forecasting is a "synthesis of planning, forecasting, step-by-step, design and other management methods" aimed at combining the efforts of the state, economic, public organizations and the scientific community in developing development priorities "[10].

Despite the development of a set of tools for public-business cooperation, at this stage, the cooperation of business structures and public organizations with government agencies faces a number of serious challenges, including:

- imperfection of the legal basis of the relationship;
- underdeveloped mechanisms and forms of partnership;

- lack of competitive conditions for effective cooperation;
- underdevelopment of investment and innovation environment, etc. "[11].

It should be noted that in order to ensure the effectiveness of cooperation between business and government, it is necessary to pay special attention to the process of managing this interaction. many barriers are marked by the fact that the government is in the area of influence on economic processes. Cooperation between private and public institutions should create the necessary conditions to increase the effectiveness of state regulation of the economy by ensuring the functioning of the feedback network and timely identification and accounting of the attitude of business entities to government decisions.

Many barriers to the development of this business are marked by the fact that the government is in the area of influence on economic processes. The interaction of private and public institutions should create the necessary conditions to increase the effectiveness of state regulation of the economy by ensuring the functioning of the feedback network and timely identification and consideration of the attitude of business entities to government decisions "[12].

Dynamic changes in economic relations "lead to the search for and use of new mechanisms and technologies to manage the interaction of economic structures with government agencies, which are currently insufficiently studied by the scientific community" [13].

A similar innovative mechanism that increases the effectiveness of cooperation between organizations and the state is GR-management (Table 1).

Table 1.

Positive results of the implementation of the GR-management mechanism *

On the scale of the national economy	On a corporate scale
- increasing the economic efficiency of the state; policy	of the corporate sector by reducing transaction costs arising from interactions with government agencies

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- consolidation of state and corporate resources; sector	increase efficiency and profitability; to reduce the impact of regulation, provide a favorable administrative climate and develop entrepreneurial activity
- state and corporate pooling resources; sector	overcoming obstacles establishing cooperative relations with the state attracting additional resources through.
- market and citizenship strengthening institutions. society	

** Author's work.*

In studying the management of public-business relations, much attention is paid to the role of government agencies in this process. However, in the scientific literature, economic societies and nonprofits

The issues of organization and management of interaction of organizations with the state are not covered. To address this imbalance, research in the field of GR has been focused.

In general, GR-management is a tool for establishing relationships between organizations and public authorities, which allows the interests of the organization to be aligned with the interests of the state. This defines the place and role of GR-management in the system of relations between the state, society and business.

GR-management ensures the coordination of the interests and efforts of the business community and the state at the macro and micro levels, which is a prerequisite for the realization of their strategic and tactical economic goals.

GR -management stems from the fact that the relationship between the state and society is a two-way process involving several entities: government agencies, the business community and public organizations. The effectiveness of their interaction depends not only on the willingness of the state, but also business and public organizations to cooperate. The purpose of GR-management is to establish a relationship between business and society with the state, to focus on the formation of business initiatives for mutually beneficial cooperation.

GR-management is the management of the organization's interaction with the state and municipalities, increasing efficiency, increasing economic profitability and minimizing the risks arising from the state.

Interaction of commercial and non-profit organizations with the state the diversity of the relationships between gives rise to their different models. Based on the author's classification of these relationships, the following models of GR management are distinguished:

- proactive model;
- reactive model;
- corporate (institutional) model;
- topic-related model;
- country (national) model.

In our opinion, the implementation of a proactive model of GR-management is an algorithmic system of interaction with the authorities, which allows to organize the relationship with the authorities on a regular basis and ensure their non-contradictory nature.

The complexity of the processes of governing social relations and economic life, as well as the strengthening of state regulation, has become a decisive factor in a new phenomenon in the theory and practice of corporate governance - (Government Relations).

From the middle of the twentieth century, the relationship of commercial and non-profit organizations with the state as the most important stakeholder of the organization began to take an institutional form, their implementation specialized units - became the right of GR-services. In a modern organization, GR is a management

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subsystem that allows the organization to reduce external risks and costs.

GR-management infrastructure in Uzbekistan is still developing. Institutional platforms have been formed, through which dialogue and interaction between business and government are carried out:

- industrial associations and unions;
- advisory councils under government agencies;
- "Open Government" and "Single Window" systems, etc.

GR-management is an interdisciplinary field of scientific research based on the principles of economic theory and management theory, as well as political science, sociology, law and others.

In our opinion, the economic and management paradigm of GR-management research is the most promising. This paradigm is based on the economic nature of GR-management, which is expressed in increasing the efficiency of the organization by reducing the organizational costs incurred in the process of interaction with public authorities through various management processes.

Theoretical and methodological bases of studying GR-management problems within the framework of economics and management paradigm include: general selection theory of economic theory and management theory, transaction cost theory, communication management theory, stakeholder theory and public-private partnership theory.

The economic and management paradigm of GR-management allows a comprehensive and complete review of its goals and objectives. In general, the purpose of GR-management is to facilitate the administrative environment and ensure mutually beneficial cooperation with government agencies, increase the efficiency and economic profitability of the organization and minimize the risks posed by the government.

To achieve this goal, it is necessary to ensure that the following tasks of GR-management are fulfilled:

- creating a single information environment between the organization and the government;
- providing information to the management of the organization on the activities of the government;
- establishing direct contacts and communication systems with government officials;
- public organizations, production and interactions with political associations;
- participation in public-private partnership programs;
- participate in the development of decisions of public authorities;
- amendments to the legislation aimed at improving the status of the organization, etc. ;
- ensuring state support (including subsidies, grants);
- obtaining assistance from the state authorities in obtaining permits, licenses for a particular type of activity by the organization;
- ensuring the receipt of government orders;

- regulatory risk management.

In the organization, GR-management performs information, analytical, communicative functions and the function of representing and protecting the interests of the organization in government agencies.

It is necessary to highlight several key elements of the GR-control mechanism (technology):

- information and analytical support of interaction with the authorities;
- organization of communication with government agencies;
- representing the interests of the organization in government and solving

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problems that arise in the process of interaction with them.

Given that these technologies are implemented in series, the implementation of each of them constitutes a phase of GR-management activities.

In the first stage of their activity, GR-managers carry out the following:

- information and analytical support of the process of interaction with the government through the collection and processing of information about the system of government and their actions;
- study of the regulatory framework;
- analysis of political processes and socio-economic dynamics;
- predicting possible decisions and actions of the authorities.

At the next stage of their activities, GR-managers organize and establish a system of communication with government agencies using the following tools:

- participate in the activities of advisory bodies in government agencies (tripartite commission, departmental commissions and councils of the republic of uzbekistan);
- participation in the oliy majlis and exhibition events;
- creation of a contractual basis for interaction, conclusion of cooperation agreements with the authorities;
- establish personal contacts with executors and participants of public policy.

The stage of representing the interests of the organization in government is the most responsible, because it is at this stage of the activities of GR-managers that the problems that arise in the process of interaction with the state are resolved. Among the methods of direct interaction with the authorities are:

- information and legal support for the solution of organizational issues in government agencies;
- negotiations with the authorities;
- influence on public authorities through the public, industrial associations, etc.

Creating an effective organizational structure of the GR department, training and retraining of GR managers is the key to external environmental safety, effective cooperation with public authorities and the successful operation of the organization.

The GR department is a structural unit of the organization that implements a set of measures for interaction with the authorities. GR departments it should be formed as part of the leading companies of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which are the largest taxpayers.

The tasks of the GR department are: to prevent unfavorable situations in the company as a result of actions of the authorities and the implementation of the necessary measures for them, to maintain a positive image of the company in the state and municipal authorities, etc.

At the present stage, the work processes of GR departments are characteristic, as such areas of GR management have undergone the greatest development, such as obtaining permits and licenses, supporting social partnership as a means of interaction with the authorities, experts. support for government activities, regional GR.

One of the specific directions of GR management in the Republic of Uzbekistan is the use of tools of corporate social responsibility. The use of the mechanism of social partnership allows the organization to create the image of a responsible participant in socio-economic processes, a reliable counterparty of government, which allows the GR-manager to increase the efficiency of its activities. Elements of corporate social responsibility include voluntary social reporting, sponsorship, and charity.

Another important area of GR management of organizations is the expert support (support) of the activities of public authorities and administration through the monitoring of existing legislation, review of draft laws and resolutions, etc. An actively developing area of government relations is regional GR.

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In order to increase the efficiency of the organization, in our opinion, it is necessary to diversify the routes, use the GR-management mechanism at the expense of investment, tax and legal spheres.

A promising area of application of GR-management methods is the field of investment. GR in carrying out investment activities the need to use these methods is often explained by the need for active interaction with public authorities for the effective implementation of the investment project. In addition, the goodwill of government agencies in the investment project can increase the profitability of the project by obtaining government benefits and preferences in the implementation of the project, including tax benefits.

GR-support measures for investment activities include a set of measures to ensure the submission of investment projects to public authorities, participation in congresses and exhibitions, participation in public-private partnerships, signing a memorandum of understanding with a public body, etc.

Another topical area of application of the GR mechanism is the tax area. The application of GR methods in the tax field allows the company to minimize tax costs. The application of GR methods in the field of taxation also ensures the balance of interests and the solution of the target tasks of all subjects of the tax process.

The tasks facing GR specialists in the field of taxation can be divided into two groups: interaction with public authorities on the optimization of the tax burden; interaction with tax authorities on tax administration issues.

Among the interrelated tasks of the tax authorities on the calculation and payment of taxes are:

- improving the efficiency of business processes as a result of cooperation with the tax service;
- creation of a system of communication with the tax service in order

to provide prompt advice on various issues in the field of taxation;

- interaction with tax inspections to ensure the impartiality of inspections;
- cooperation with tax authorities on tax calculation;
- resolution of situations arising as a result of technical failures, illegal actions of the taxpayer or tax inspector.

An important area for improving the work of GR-managers is to further deepen the work in the legal field. In addressing company issues, GR managers should use a variety of legal means of interaction between the business community and the state, such as law enforcement, the institution of self-regulatory organizations, public examination of draft regulations, contracting with the government, etc.

It is also necessary to use various legal means of interaction with the authorities. It should be noted that due to the constructive dialogue between the institutions of business, government and civil society, the current legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan is dynamically improving, creating new institutions of transparent interaction.

The purpose of the study of the effective use of the GR-management mechanism for the development of the state, society and business is to develop scientific and practical recommendations to highlight current trends in the formation and effective operation of the GR-management mechanism as a tool for managing the enterprise's interaction with the state.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks must be performed:

- to study the concepts and models of the system of interaction of the business community and the social sector with the authorities;
- scientific interpretation of the categorical description of the essence and content of GR-management;
- substantiate the diversification of methodological approaches to the study of GR-management;

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- formation of mechanisms and models of GR-management: implementation of a comparative analysis of foreign experience and practice of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- scientific interpretation of the quality description of GR-management technologies and tools;
- clarification of the features of the organization and operation of the GR-service at the enterprise;
- scientific substantiation of the decomposition of the main directions of GR-management in ensuring the balanced development of the state, society and business in the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- development of a set of recommendations aimed at improving the effectiveness of the use of GR-management methods.

Conclusions and suggestions

In the framework of the new management policy in the context of modernization and liberalization of the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, taking into account the current challenges of socio-economic development, "GR" - Development of an improved mechanism through the coordination and harmonization of vital factors such as "management mechanism", "GR-management technologies and tools in effective areas of public-private partnership", "openness of the economy and the business environment", and this process allows you to:

-systematic approach provides a new interpretation of the concepts of "GR-management mechanism as a tool for managing the interaction of the enterprise with the state", "GR-service in the enterprise", which includes an improved terminological apparatus developed;

- scientific analysis of the factors determining the need for a new approach to the study of modern trends in the organization of GR-management as a tool for managing the interaction of the enterprise with the state in the Republic of Uzbekistan

and substantiate their effective management measures;

- a methodology for assessing the prospects and effectiveness of corporate governance will be developed to identify current trends and priorities for the formation and effective operation of the GR-management mechanism as a tool for managing the interaction of the enterprise with the state, ensuring the laws of balanced development of the state, society and business;

- prospects for the use of advanced foreign experience in the context of Uzbekistan in the context of modern trends in the formation and effective operation of the GR-management mechanism as a tool for managing the interaction of the enterprise with the state;

- on the basis of a new conceptual scheme of studying the interrelationship of various factors, a system of complex measures will be developed to implement medium and long-term tasks to improve the current trends in the formation and effective functioning of the GR-management mechanism as a tool for managing enterprise interaction with the state.

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